

Dalit and contemporary issues in India

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ABSTRACT:

Nowadays in India there is the situation that makes the unity and prestigious matter a disgusting one. The main issue is the exploitation and underrated attitude towards the Dalits, who are among the 80% of the residents of India. They are the rural area people who are mainly illiterate and usually find the exploitation against them are their fate. A numerous reform movements had started for their reformation and to make them aware of their rights which are included in the constitution of India. Many reformers had contributed for these reforms and had tried hard for the sake of Dalits, but the activities against Dalits are more and more agitative nowadays. The recent issues of Madhu in Kerala and some incidents that had occurred in our country made these things worse than ever. In our country the Dalit movements had become a riddle and there were no benefits for Dalits occurred.

KEYWORDS:

Dalit movement, Exploitation, Agitative, Religious rituals, Blind belief

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India, our country is famous for its unity among the people, religion and all. It is considered as the country bearing uniformity in eternity, the tag line which made the country's unity to the next level. Among the one twenty crores of people about 80% of the people of the remote rural area are to be considered as to be illiterate and they are getting avoided from any of the rights and rewards all the normal people do get. They are to be regarded as the Dalits who are born to be get exploited and suffer the cruel behavior of

all the other people.

The country in which the caste system was formed as the medium for getting jobs easily according to their names such as Shudras, Kshatriyas, Brahmins and so. The arrival of Aryans made a lot difference in this system of caste. They made it according to the religion in order to exploit the so-called lower people on the basis of their Varna. The Aryans made them suffer a lot within this system. The famous quote from the Bhagavad Gita shows the basis of caste system and that of the Varnas.

“Chatur- varnyam maya srushtam guna-

Karma – vibhagashah

Tasya kartaram api mam viddhyakartaram avyayam”¹

{The four categories of occupations were created by me according to people’s qualities and activities. Although I am the creator of this system, know me to be the Non-doer and Eterna.}

The four varnas were created then is only for the convenience of their work. Then years passed the system became more and more complicated as the Aryans who are so-called upper caste people change in accordance to their superiority. As the era of Aryans declined the system of four varnas never ailed their existence in our country. This became very vicious during post freedom even after the framing of Constitution. Even though the laws are made for the betterment of the Dalit people it also failed to protect them. This in fact led to the wide discriminations all over the Country.

Then came an angel for the Dalits in the name of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, who also belong to the so-called lower community raise his voice against the discrimination which made some relief in the minds of people of lower community. He gave the awareness regarding the rights of Dalits mentioned in the constitution to his

people. As a result, many more reform movements had begun in our country. Thus, Ambedkar began to be called “The Father of Dalit Reforms in India”. He encouraged his people with the slogan:

“Educate, Agitate, Organize”²

The slogan formulates the minds of Dalit people in India and thus they in accordance to the guidance of Ambedkar many reform movements started to get organized all over the country. The slogan created by the Father of Constitution and Dalit movement generated a widespread agitation throughout the Country. This even resulted in bringing the faith in the minds of Dalit people regarding to their rights and even to raise their voice against the torture they face.

Even though these reform movements had been taken place in the country, the situation of Dalits in India prevails the same. There is only a slight difference from the older days which is most of them has become educated and are aware of the fundamental rights that they possess in the country. Many social reformers in order to serve the welfare of Dalit people in India got united and a well-organized reform institution are formed throughout the country. Jyotiba Phule, Savthribhai Phule, Raja Ram Mohan Roy and many other reformers made their way towards the welfare of Dalits in India.

“It is necessary that some change should take place in their religion”.³

There are many examples of caste discrimination faced by Dalits in India today. This is because from them most are illiterate even today. They only know that what they suffer is the continuation that their previous era of people had suffered.

Even now they consider it as their fate to tolerate all the nonsense. India has a value and strong Constitution within to maintain

the Democracy in our country. Within five decades the discriminations found many ways particularly by the upper caste people to the lower caste people (Dalits) they are excluded the own people in India. The lower Dalit people are also subjected to the discriminations by the people in their community itself. They are subjected to be banned from even the rituals and the functions that ever happened in their own community. This led to the total untouchability in India. Nowadays also this system prevails in our Country, as some of the North Indian as well as South Indian states make use of this. The Constitution of India has thoroughly made the rights and punishments regarding the protection of Dalits but they are found to be inadequate in the current Indian society.

“Even Dalits and Adivasis have been assaulted and abused on the false grab of Covid 19. Violations of their fundamental human rights continue unabated during the lockdown. Atrocities have been perpetrated against them and in most of the cases police and higher authorities have been complacent.” 4

There are many issues relating to Dalits in India. They are widespread discrimination, social exclusion, economic marginalization, violence, lack of access to education and employment opportunities, particularly affecting the women with relevant issues like caste based sexual violence, forced labor and limited legal resource against perpetrators, all stemming from the deeply entrenched caste system despite legal protections against and untouchability. Most of the women face such methods of discrimination throughout their work home in society etc. Though all the members of the family and work place know that, even then nobody raises voice against them. This is the issues related to the Dalit women in India. This is much harsh than the things women suffered during old days. Again, if we gather information about the caste discrimination towards the women in their neighborhood and even in the society. In another

case if the men are getting such ideas and rude ideologies from the pre-existing policies, then the life of women in the society said to be in a state of distress and pain. cruelty that are caused during the golden era. Now also the Dalit are getting as much torture that they all suffer in the past, but how can we stop the discrimination that is based on the caste and varnas. If we got to know the recent case of Madhu, in Kerala who had been killed by other people beating him for just taking food as he was starving. This is one of the examples of Dalit discrimination that had ever happened during the twentieth century in so called literary India.

The most recent violations against the Dalit people are regarding to that of Women and children. The violations against the Children are the most widespread problem nowadays. Mostly in the schools they face discriminations and abuses.

They suffer abuses and rude behavior not only by the students but also by the teachers. They create a vicious environment for those children who came from the Dalit community by the regarding scholarships from the Government itself. Even from the report “The quest for justice” also states that the children from these lower communities faces mentally both mental and physical abuses from the upper caste people. Untouchability is the concept that prevails in the context of Indian Democratic system even though the rules and regulations in India are against it. There are so many acts that are made in this context to make the rights of the Dalits available in the society. Nowadays the act of untouchability is continued in the various areas of our country which remarks a red mark in the unity in sovereignty of our country. Lots of issues are reporting after the acts made for the protection of rights of Dalit and such tribes in India. Another crime against the Dalits is the misusing of the rights mentioned in the act and lack of information about the act. There are so many claims appearing among the upper caste

people saying that the Dalits are misusing the rights made for them. “Lots of issues to implement this act due to lack of interest by the State not providing the infrastructures and equipment this degrade things also continues in our country.”⁵

Generally, Dalits are subjected to various kinds of caste-oriented discrimination these are now prevailing in the villages. In many places they are even banned from entering the temples as well as attending any functions within the villages. There are many cases that involve these types of caste determined actions reported. Dalits also face many victimizations that led by the Hindus in many forms. They are even banned from entering the ration shops that gave them the life supporting system. These types of many cases are reported even now in our Country which is known for considering all the human same in its vision. Dalit identity assertion and their struggles for equality in political economic social religious health and education leading towards societal transformation. Certainly, it is going to create a revolution among people in the near future and it will be witnessed in Indian history. The stigma of considering Dalits as regardless victims continues in India. The women are particularly badly affected in recent times. They are discriminated against not only because of their sex but also because of religious social and cultural structures which have given them the lowest position in the social hierarchy. The stigma of ‘untouchability’ exposes them to an even highest risk of abuse and exploitation.

The country should give the Dalits the respect and the rights that they ever needed in their whole life. None should be given the rights to exploit them in any parts of our country, if so, they should be punished by the law and order. The Dalits and women should be considered as equal to that of any other citizen in the Country. They should be given the equal rights for education and even marriages in this Country. Not only the women, but the children should be

given their rights and their dignity, even for education as well as other children in the Country.

Conclusion:

The Dalits in Contemporary India are facing many issues and challenges nowadays. In them the stigma of untouchability is remaining the same as in the olden days. The Dalits are subjected to many problems even though they are given many rights and reservations in the Constitution itself. In many North Indian states such as Uttar Pradesh, Bihar are going through the struggles related towards the Dalits. The women in that societies are facing even worse situations such as gang rape, getting rejected in the fields of education and so.

The Dalits must still make the core, major effort, with ever better education, to recover and remake their inner self. There is now a crying need to access the corresponding rights and to resume their position in our country. The Dalits are constitutently being suffering the sabotages from the upper caste people who still make a domain over the so-called Dalits who are being forced for to have a miseries life. There should be a movement that helps in the transformation of Dalits in Contemporary India. There are many rights and acts which are made for the construction of new life in the Country, but that doesn't affect the upper-class people or even the Government or their policies which are made for the Dalits. Even in South India the Dalits are suffering the stigma of untouchability prevails in India. The Dalits in South India suffer even from the stage of not getting food for their hunger. The incident of Madhu, who was killed for taking food from a shop in order to control his hunger, states the miserable condition of the Dalits in Kerala (South Indian state).

Thus, the challenges and disputes of Dalits are continuing as

the previous types in our country, which being not interrogated by the Government or even the laws made by them. So, the problems of the Dalits should be get controlled by the Government amendments.

Endnote:

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